

THE BASICS OF STYLISTIC DEVICES IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

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Abstract. The article examines the main classifications of stylistic devices in English literature based on the works of J. Leach, I.R. Galperin and Yu.M. Skrebnev.

Key words: classification, stylistic devices, figures of speech, tropes, types of speech.

When studying the language features of a particular author, it is necessary to refer to the works of famous linguists-stylists and study the classifications of stylistic devices and expressive means. This contributes to a better understanding of the linguistic means chosen by the writer and a more thorough analysis of stylistic devices at all levels of the language.

Today, there is no unified approach to the classification of stylistic devices in domestic and foreign stylistics. It is worth noting that the beginning of modern classifications was laid by the Hellenistic Roman system of rhetoric, within the framework of which all expressive means are divided into three groups: tropes, rhythm (figures of speech) and types of speech. And one of the first linguists who attempted to modernize the Hellenistic Roman system of rhetoric and developed a modern classification was Geoffrey Leach, a famous British scientist. Drawing on the principles of descriptive linguistics, popular at the time, he attempted to show how linguistic theory could be linked to the task of describing such rhetorical figures as metaphor, parallelism, alliteration, personification, and others in the study of literature [2]. According to J. Leach, writers and poets use language in a non-standard way and allow a certain degree of "poetic license". The language of literature as a whole is marked by a number of deviant features. Thus, D. Leach builds his classification on the principle of the difference between normal and deviant features in the language of literature [1].

Among the deviant features he distinguishes paradigmatic and syntagmatic deviations. First of all, we distinguish different levels of linguistic function, at which a figure is to be identified and described. Based on this, these figures are classified as formal (grammatical or lexical), phonological, orthographic or semantic, or perhaps a combination of these categories. Linguistic units are linked syntagmatically when they are successively combined

in a linear linguistic form. Paradigmatic elements enter into a system of possible choices at one point in the chain. Syntagmatic elements can be considered horizontally, paradigmatic ones vertically. Paradigmatic elements give the writer a choice of equivalent items that contrast with the usual choice. For example, certain nouns can usually be followed by certain adverbs, the choice being determined by their normal lexical valence. However, the author's choice of noun can disrupt the normal system and create a paradigmatic deviation, which we encounter in literary and poetic language [3].

Yu. M. Skrebnev does not divide expressive means and stylistic devices into the corresponding layers of language, as I. R. Galperin does. He first divides stylistics into paradigmatic stylistics (or stylistics of units) and syntagmatic stylistics (or stylistics of sequences). Then he examines the level of language and considers all stylistically significant phenomena in accordance with these levels, both in paradigmatic and syntagmatic stylistics. He also clearly identifies one more level. In addition to phonetics, lexicology and syntax, he adds semantics [3].

The classification of stylistic devices proposed by I.R. Galperin is characterized by a high degree of detail, includes the following division of expressive means and stylistic devices based on a level approach:

Thus, it can be concluded that there are various classifications of stylistic devices and expressive means. Three modern classifications of expressive means of the English language were proposed by J. Leach, I. R. Galperin and Yu. M. Skrebnev. J. Leach's classification is based on the principle of distinguishing between normal and abnormal features of the literary language. He identified paradigmatic and syntagmatic deviations from the lexical and grammatical norms of the language. I. R. Galperin based his classification on a level-by-level approach and identified three groups: phonetic, lexical, syntactic expressive means and stylistic devices. The methodology of Yu. M. Skrebnev demonstrates a combination of the principles of J. Leach's paradigmatic and syntagmatic division and I. R. Galperin's level-by-level approach

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